

Jugyou Kenkyuu: A Tool for Differentiating Mathematics Instruction

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 20, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 21, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Differentiated, Instruction, Mathematics, Jugyoukenkyuu</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6875992</p>	<p><i>This study determined the effectiveness of JugyouKenkyuu, a school-based teacher's professional development activity cycle, on selected topics in senior high school's General Mathematics among the selected senior high school Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics students at Palawan National School, Palawan, Philippines. The quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design utilizing a teacher-made test was employed. Means, standard deviations, and t-test for two independent samples was used to analyze and interpret the gathered data. The students in the control and experimental groups were comparable in their mathematics performance before the experiment. The students exposed to JugyouKenkyuu mathematics instruction significantly had higher achievement than those exposed to the traditional teaching approach. The study concludes that JugyouKenkyuu is a better teaching approach in developing the students' cognitive skills to understand General Mathematics and improve their mathematics performance. Lastly, JugyouKenkyuu Mathematics Instruction can guide mathematics teachers to develop students' mathematical competence, performance, and better understanding.</i></p>

Introduction

Teacher professional development has been a constant prime concern in the education sector. Several studies have focused on teachers' effectiveness in recent years as recognized to ascertain students' achievement. It is believed that teachers' effectiveness can be achieved by grounding professional development in actual classroom practice. Japanese Lesson Study is the direct translation for the term JugyouKenkyuu. In Japanese, the word Jugyou means lesson, and Kenkyuu means to study or research. It was decades since Japan has pioneered such an effort to address this educational objective through their specific professional development program called JugyouKenkyuu or Lesson Study. This program has been delineated as a way of teacher development and collaboration based on class observation and critique. In the original context, Lewis et al. (2013) explained Lesson Study terms and key features into JugyouKenkyuu, meaning lesson research or lesson study, which refers to the actual classroom lessons that teachers planned together and discussed. JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) refers to instructional improvement, of which the research lesson is the main element.

Mathematics achievement of students is a concern among educators all over the world most especially in the Philippines. Filipino learners register low Performance in Mathematics at almost all levels nationwide. The poor performance in the National Achievement Test (NAT) from 50.7% in the school year 2007 – 2008 to 46.3% in the school year 2011 – 2012 of high schools in the Philippines and its low rank of 115th out of 142 states in the Global Competitiveness Report confirms this claim.

Over recent years, policymakers nationwide have begun to focus on helping teachers cope with the advanced methods and approaches for engaging diverse students in mastering challenging subject content and necessary skills. In Japan, the lesson study approach to teaching has been firmly established to improve teachers' Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK). According to Richardson (2013), lesson study or also called "JugyouKenkyuu," is a school-based teacher's professional development activity cycle that showcases teacher's value of working together while sharing personal classroom experiences and observing each other teachers while teaching.

The Programme for International Student Assessment's 2018 results showed that the Philippines attained a score of 357 in Science, 353 in Mathematics, and 340 in Reading, which is all below the average of participating OECD countries. The PISA results reflect our learners' performance in the National Achievement Test; DepEd recognizes the urgency of addressing issues and gaps in attaining primary education quality in the Philippines. Department of Education will lead this national effort for quality primary education through *SulongEdukalidad* by implementing aggressive reforms in four key areas such: K to 12 reviews, Improvement of learning facilities, Teachers and school heads' upskilling and reskilling through a transformed professional development program; and engagement of all stakeholders for support and collaboration.

The researchers have noticed that most Grade 11 Senior high School Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) students at Palawan National School, Philippines have poor performance in General Mathematics. As mathematics teachers, the desire to reach more students and increase their achievement levels has motivated the researchers to address this concern by applying the *JugyouKenkyuu* (Lesson Study) approach in teaching mathematics to systematically understand mathematics and systematically improve their mathematics performance. This issue in the Department of education has not only happened at Palawan National School but also in the whole elementary and secondary sectors nationwide. This is supported by Filipino students' mathematics achievement scores, whether in local or international examinations, to reveal a low-performance rate. The National Achievement Test (NAT) results for Grade 6 in SY 2009-2010 showed a passing rate of only 69.21% while the result for high school was only 46.38% in SY 2009-2010. Moreover, among the 38 countries which participated in the 2003 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), the Philippines ranked 34th in HS II Math. In 2008, the Philippines ranked last among the ten participating countries. (Department of Education, 2010).

JugyouKenkyuu

JugyouKenkyuu or Lesson Study is a teacher professional development model widely used by Japanese teachers, wherein they conduct a systematic study into their pedagogical practices through a close examination of their lessons (Saito and Atencio, 2013). In lesson study, a group or team composed of three to five professional teachers, usually within the same grade level, meet regularly and collaboratively investigate a "research lesson" designed to impact student achievement (Cheung and Wong, 2014). Initially, the professional group works together to identify a curricular goal within a content area and set goals for improvement (Saito and Atencio, 2013).

The principles of lesson study conform to the idea that learning is a social and situated process. For teachers, the classroom is the best venue for them to learn and improve their teaching style and practices. It follows a cyclical process which involves: 1) collaborative goal setting and planning the study lesson (Fernandez and Yoshida, 2004) or research lesson (Lewis, 2006); 2) implementing and observing the research study; 3) reflecting on the observed lesson; 4) modifying and revising the research lesson (optional); 5) teaching the modified research lesson (optional or whenever required), and 6) lastly, teacher's post-lesson reflection and discussion.

As a professional development strategy, *JugyouKenkyuu* (Lesson Study) is used to promote the development of teachers' Mathematical Pedagogical Content Knowledge and assist them in differentiating mathematics instruction. Differentiated Mathematics Instruction was chosen as a strategy to facilitate meeting diverse student needs in a regular classroom. Thus, Lesson Study can be a vehicle to improve teacher knowledge and skills, which will impact student learning development, especially in mathematics in this case, through differentiated learning.

The University of the Philippines' National Institute of Science and Mathematics Education Development (UP-NISMED) has been strongly advocating *JugyouKenkyuu*. In their intensive study involving public school chemistry teachers, *JugyouKenkyuu* presents strong evidence of teachers' effectiveness, as seen in student achievement. This is tenacious with the claim of Darling-Hammond (2009) that teacher qualities are essential determinants of student achievement. The teacher's teaching and learning process bring along the knowledge components.

Since then, many Mathematics educators worldwide have been involved in introducing Lesson Study to approach teacher professional development. Lesson Study is credited with enabling profound changes in Mathematics and Science teaching in Japan in recent decades – a fact evidenced by Japan's high levels of achievement in international assessments over the past 20 years.

Constructivism

The theory of Constructivism by Vygotsky states that knowledge is constructed based on social interactions and experience. Ability reflects the outside world as filtered through and influenced by culture, language, beliefs, and interactions with others, direct teaching, and modeling [9] (Woolfolk, 2014). He also believed that understanding how learner views the world; a teacher must first understand something about the learner's home and peer group's culture.

For Piaget's points of view about Constructivism, he emphasized that teachers should support students in exploring and developing understanding. He focused his study on the individual's inner working as the learner actively constructed his knowledge through the various stages of cognitive development [10] (Parsons et al.,

2001). Both Vygotsky and Piaget pointed out a model that teachers serve as facilitators and guides rather than directors and molder of children's learning (Santrock, 2009).

Constructivism by Dewey is problem-based, adaptive learning that challenges faulty schema integrates new knowledge with existing knowledge, and allows for original work or innovative procedures. Learners are self-directed, creative, innovative, drawing upon visual/spatial/ musical/rhythmic, bodily-kinesthetic, verbal/linguistic, logical/mathematical, interpersonal/intrapersonal, and naturalistic. Education aims to become creative and innovative through analysis, conceptualizations, and prior experience to create new knowledge. The educator's role is to guide each learner during heuristic problem solving of ill-defined problems by enabling quested learning. The learning objective is the highest order of education: heuristic problem solving, metacognitive knowledge, creativity, and originality that may modify existing knowledge and create a new experience.

Discovery Approach

This study is also anchored on the discovery approach as its inductive method of guiding students to organize ideas. The discovery approach is how the students or learners under subtle direction go through the logical process of observation, comparison, abstraction, generalization, and application. As an alternative to telling either by the teacher or explaining textbooks, self-discovery sets up learning situations whereby students are encouraged to explore a process or discover rules.

Experiential Learning Theory

Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory helps elaborate how experienced is changed into learning and reliable knowledge. He added that truth is not manifest in experience; it must be inferred by the process of learning that questions preconception of direct experience, tempers the vividness and emotion of experience which critical reflections, and extracts the correct lessons from the consequences of actions (Kolb, 2014).

Pedagogical Content

Hill et al. (2013) said that pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) is an essential and critical element in determining a teacher's success in handling the teaching and learning process and further produce effective teaching. Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) has been qualified as a deeply personal, highly contextualized, and influenced by teaching interaction and experiences. Therefore, the lesson study approach to teaching can be a timely effort to enhance teachers' competence, especially in Mathematics and Science education, since it is highly structured to involve teachers' collaborative interaction and sharing of experiences based on actual teaching.

Mathematical Pedagogical Content Knowledge has been chosen as a critical facet of this study because it is used to differentiate mathematics instruction. In this study, Mathematical Pedagogical Content Knowledge includes mathematical content knowledge, mathematical pedagogical knowledge, and mathematical context knowledge. Mathematical content knowledge consists of mathematical, conceptual experience, which is a teacher's understanding of the concept of the topic being taught, and mathematics procedural knowledge, which shows a teacher's knowledge of the procedure of the mathematics topic being taught. Mathematical pedagogical knowledge is knowledge about teaching mathematics. It covers students' learning, mathematics teaching strategies, and curriculum knowledge. Knowledge of students is about knowing how students think about the mathematics topic they are learning. Mathematical context knowledge is the knowledge that teachers need to have regarding the environment surrounding the classroom that may influence teaching and learning. This knowledge includes central and local government regulations and an understanding of the community that may impact student learning.

Differentiated learning

Differentiated learning leads to students being engaged in tasks that are based on their level. Students become engrossed because the job is enjoyable, or because it seems to provide them with the power of competence of autonomy, or because it links with experience, interest, or talent that is significant to them, and to challenge and stimulate rather than to frustrate or bore them (Tomlinson, 2013).

Learning Mathematics is the number one factor why students are hesitant to pursue their college education, aside from being affected by their socio-economic status. This difficulty in acquiring knowledge would always depend on how that information is being transferred to the students. It has been perceived that Filipino students perform poorly in Mathematics. According to the international test conducted by TIMSS in 2010, only 1% of Filipino students reached the advanced level in high school math performance, and the Philippines got the

lowest-ranked. As part of the government's efforts to respond to the sector's perceived needs, the Department of Education (DepED) implemented the K to 12 Basic Education Program. One of the curriculum's highlighted changes is integrating the advanced mathematics curriculum exceptionally, precalculus, general mathematics, essential Calculus, statistics, and probability in senior high school. Knowledge in mathematics provides leverage for learners who want to have a better career in the future. To aid and prepare them, teachers must engage those students and ignite their enthusiasm to learn more about mathematics. They must strengthen Filipino students' belief that through effort, they can increase their mathematical ability and that word problems should not be neglected.

Differentiated Mathematics Instruction has been chosen as a strategy to facilitate meeting diverse student needs in a regular classroom. Differentiation includes content, process, product, assessment, and learning environment differentiation (Tomlinson, 2003), considering student profiles, school environment and facilities, and the national curriculum.

This study involved three main ideas: JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study), Mathematical Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), and Differentiated Instruction (DI). These ideas' relationship can be seen by describing Lesson Study as the vehicle to improve teachers' mathematical Pedagogical Content Knowledge for differentiating mathematics instruction.

The Statement of the Problem

The study determined the JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) effectiveness in selected topics in Senior High School's General Mathematics among the selected Senior High School Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) students of Palawan National School, Puerto Princesa, Palawan, Philippines.

The study sought answers for the following questions:

1. What is the pretest performance of the control and experimental groups?
2. What is the posttest Performance of the control and experimental groups?
3. Do students have significantly higher achievement when exposed to JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) mathematics instruction than those exposed to the traditional teaching approach?
4. What Differentiated Instruction lesson plan in Mathematics may be proposed?

Statement of the Null Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Students do not have significantly higher achievement when exposed to JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) mathematics instruction than those exposed to the traditional teaching approach.

Method

Research Design

The study utilized the quasi-experimental method to assess the effectiveness of the JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) approach in teaching Senior High School General Mathematics with a researcher-made test. The data is taken from the pretest and posttest to determine whether JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) approach can develop the cognitive skills in understanding General Mathematics and improve their mathematics performance. In this research design, there are two kinds of groups: the experimental group exposed to JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) and the control group exposed to traditional teaching methods. Figure 1 shows the research flow.

Figure 1. The Research Flow

Research Environment

This study was conducted in one of the national schools in Puerto Princesa City, Palawan, Philippines. Palawan Island is the largest island in the Philippines. This island has been rated by National Geographic Traveler magazine as best Southeast Asia region in 2007, and the 13th best island in the world! Due to amazing landscapes and high bio-diversity, Palawan island is known as “The Last Ecological Frontier of the Philippines”.

Specifically, the study was conducted at Palawan National School (PNS) in Puerto Princesa City, Palawan, Philippines. It is the most prominent public high school in Puerto Princesa City. This school now has more than 9,000 students. It is a premier school in Palawan that aims to provide quality education for students' development. The study limits itself to senior high school students in Palawan, Philippines studying General Mathematics.

Research Subjects

Two sections were randomly selected from the eight blocks of Grade 11 Senior High School STEM Students of Palawan National School and identified as the control (STEM 113) and the experimental (STEM 115) group using the lottery method. Some 40 students represented the control group with pretest and posttest (control pre-post group) and 40 students for the experimental group with pretest and posttest (experimental pre-post group) during the first semester of the school year 2019-2020.

Research Instrument

A teacher-made test, multiple choice type with 40 items, was used. The test is composed of knowledge and process level of concept development. The test questions were solicited from the mathematics teachers and master teachers who taught the subject and were based on the covered competencies found in the Table of Specifications. The lessons covered in the test are functions; rational functions; exponential, inverse, and logarithmic functions which are topics in the first quarter for the General Mathematics subject.

Likewise, the teacher-made test was subjected to content and face validation by two master teachers and experts in Mathematics. Afterwards, it was presented to a panel member who is an expert in teaching Mathematics. Subsequent revisions and polishing were made to comply with the recommendations of the evaluators. After the modifications, the teacher-made test was pilot tested to other sections which the researcher did not handle in order to check its reliability. ACronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.87 was obtained and is interpreted as Good internal consistency.

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission and approval to conduct the study were sought from the principal of the Palawan National School, Puerto Princesa, Palawan, Philippines. After the approval, the researchers made the learning activity sheets suitable for three (3) months on functions; rational functions; exponential, inverse, and logarithmic functions topics in the General Mathematics subject before the test was conducted.

The researchers personally administered the pretest to the control group and experimental groups in Grade 11 Senior High School students. After the conduct of the pretest, a t-test of independent means on the significance of the difference between the two groups' pretest scores was done to test comparability. The results revealed no significant difference. Thus, the two groups are comparable, and therefore the experiment can proceed.

After the pretesting, the control group was exposed to the traditional method of teaching, which means 80 percent lecture and 20 percent activity, while the experimental group was exposed to the application of the JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) approach, which represents 80 percent activity and only 20 percent for the clarificatory session. This method is cited by Bacalso (2017) in his study Problem-Based Learning (PBL) Approach in teaching Statistics. Both groups were using the same type of learning materials as their detailed lesson plan. Afterward, the posttest was administered to measure the performances of the control and experimental groups. The examination paper was checked immediately and analyzed.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics using the Analysis Tool Pack as an add-in of the Microsoft EXCEL were employed to analyze data. Means, standard deviations, frequencies and percentages were used to determine the profile of the

traditional and experimental groups in their pretest and the posttest scores. There are four levels of performance, namely Very Good (with raw scores 30 – 40), Good (with raw scores 20 – 29), Fair (with raw scores 10 – 19), and Poor (with raw scores 0 – 9). Inferential statistics was utilized for the analysis of the significance of the difference in the control and experimental groups' performance with the t-test of independent means as treatment.

Results and Discussion

The results on the pretest and posttest performance of the control and experimental groups as well as the significance of the difference in performance when exposed to *Jugyou Kenkyuu* (Lesson Study) mathematics instruction and when exposed to the traditional teaching approach are herein discussed.

The Pretest Performance

The pretest scores of the control and experimental groups are summarized in Table 1. There were 40 research subjects in the control group. It can be seen that in this control group, majority, 32 students (80.00%) got a score of 10 to 19 and described as Fair performance; There was one student (2.50%) who got a score between 0 to 9 and interpreted as Poor performance.

On the other hand, in the experimental group with $n=40$ research subjects, it can be gleaned in Table 1 that majority still, 33 students (82.50%), got a score of 10 – 19 and described as Fair performance, although there was one student (2.50%) who got a score of 30 to 40 and interpreted as Very Good performance. No student performed poorly.

Table 1. Pretest Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups

Performance	Score	Control		Experimental	
		f	%	f	%
Very Good	30 – 40	0	0.00	1	2.50
Good	20 – 29	7	17.50	6	15.00
Fair	10 – 19	32	80.00	33	82.50
Poor	0 – 9	1	2.50	0	0.00
Total		40	100.00	40	100.00
n			40		40
Mean			15.28		15.95
Standard Deviation			3.97		4.62

It can also be observed from Table 1 that the mean score and standard deviation in the control group were 15.28 and 3.97, respectively. In contrast, the experimental group, had a mean score of 15.95 and a standard deviation of 4.62. The data revealed that the performance of most of the students in the control and experimental groups belong to Fair performance in the pretest, and the standard deviation shows the homogeneity of pretest performance.

The results of the pretest imply that both groups are on an equal footing to be used in the experiment. Thus, the groups are comparable. Further, the results agree with Schlich (2015) in her study about analyzing the Pretest and Posttest performance of learners in a Learning Center Model at the elementary school level. She noted in the implications for future research that students should take an assessment that is the same as the pretest to show their growth accurately. This will allow the researcher to truly study the individual student's development after receiving the intervention.

The Posttest Performance

The posttest performance of the control and experimental groups are summarized in Table 2. It is revealed that in the control group, majority, 25 students (62.50%), got a score of 20 to 29 and described as Good performance. No one had a Poor performance.

Table 2. Posttest Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups

Performance	Score	Control		Experimental	
		f	%	f	%
Very Good	30 – 40	11	27.50	32	80.00
Good	20 – 29	25	62.50	8	20.00
Fair	10 – 19	4	10.00	0	0.00

Poor	0 – 9	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total		40	100.00	40	100.00
n			40	40	
Mean			28.58	34.93	
Standard Deviation			4.76	3.91	

It can be gleaned that the mean score of the control group was 28.58 and interpreted as Good. The standard deviation was 4.76, with scores a bit spread. Meanwhile in the experimental group it had a mean score of 34.93, interpreted as Very Good and a standard deviation of 3.91. The data revealed that there is an increase in the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups.

It can be noted that there were 32 students (80.00%) who got a score of 30 to 40 and described as Very Good performance and eight students (20.00%) who garnered a score of 20 to 29 and described as Good performance in the experimental group. However, more students showed excellent performances in the experimental group than in the control group. This signifies that JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) is better than the traditional teaching approach.

The results of the posttest are supported by Aritonang (2008), who believes that teachers play an essential role in improving students' interest and motivating learning mathematics. One effective way of improving student engagement may be for teachers to differentiate mathematics instruction so that it can address the needs of all learners in regular classrooms and enhance the learning outcomes of the students (Tomlinson & Eidson, 2003).

In Vygotsky's social constructivist view of development, the idea of learning is the output of collaborative problem – solving and is facilitated by using activities that are unique and authentic. The subsequent interaction of one's knowledge and others' knowledge created opportunities for a fresh and new experience. Also, the Zone of Proximal Development of Vygotsky did not just apply to the students' zone, but also the teaching team worked within their zones, which brought better output (Harland, 2003).

Moreover, differentiated teaching is different from traditional education and does not necessarily involve direct instruction. It uses similar content but utilizes diverse cognitive thinking levels for other groups (Bender, 2009). Teachers adjust their activities to cater to students' readiness, interests, and learning styles. Subsequently, they can deliver effective teaching, improve students' interests, and realize their hidden interests (Tomlinson & Eidson, 2003).

The Significance of the Difference Between the Posttest Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups

In order to determine the significance of the difference between the control and experimental group posttest performances the one-tailed t-test of independent means was used. The results are given in Table 3 which shows that the mean of the experimental group is higher than the mean of the control group. The computed p-value of 3.5932E-09 is less than the alpha level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$, which leads to the null hypothesis' rejection. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups fails to be rejected. It implies that the experimental group performed better than the control group. The students exposed to JugyouKenkyuu mathematics instruction significantly have higher achievement than those exposed to the traditional teaching approach and that JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) is useful. JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) is a great potential in improving the student's learning outcomes.

Table 3. t-test of the Significance of the Difference between the Posttests of the Control and Experimental Groups

	<i>Control</i>	<i>Experimental</i>
Mean	28.575	34.925
Variance	22.66089744	15.25064103
Observations	40	40
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	75	
t Stat	-6.522559007	
P(T<=t) one-tail	3.5932E-09	
t Critical one-tail	1.665425374	
P(T<=t) two-tail	7.19E-09	
t Critical two-tail	1.992102124	

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significance of the difference between the the posttests of the control and experimental groups agree with [19] Harsono (2016), who revealed in her study that Lesson Study could be a vehicle for enhancing teachers' knowledge of mathematical content, pedagogical, and context to differentiate the content, process, product, assessment, and learning environment in mathematics lessons in heterogeneous classrooms.

The study of Solomon and Ramo (2005) agrees with the findings of the research. They measured the effects of Differentiated Instruction (DI) on students' achievement in the Department of the Education's University of Mindanao during the 2nd term of S.Y. 2004 – 2005. There are three kinds of questionnaires used in data collection and gathering with mean, t-test for a dependent, and independent means as statistical tools. By using experimental design, results showed that DI's use was significantly more effective than the traditional approach in improving students' achievement in Basic Mathematics. Hence, appropriate training in Differentiated Instruction is recommended with other subjects like English and Filipino to validate this study's outcome.

The results also agreed with Cannon (2017) cited in her research that it is no longer good to let the students sit idle in their desks with a worksheet. Students, when provided with an engaging environment, become immersed in their learning. In the nineteenth-century, teachers were of two types: the intellectual overseer, who stressed memorization and punished failure in assignments, and the drillmaster, who had the students repeat material in unison. Educators can no longer afford to be the intellectual overseer or the drillmaster. They must provide diverse education based on our student's strengths and weaknesses and varied opportunities for students to be active in the learning practice promoting their strengths in each task.

Creating an effectively differentiated course is one-way that teachers can support individual students working at their optimal challenge zone. Differentiation, as a pedagogical strategy, developed by Carol Ann Tomlinson, a professor from the University of Virginia, asserts that the teacher makes a special effort to understand, appreciate, and build upon student differences. The teacher designs the course of instruction, specifically, to encourage all learners to work at a level that is appropriately challenging to them for maximum growth and individual success (Tomlinson and Edison, 2003).

JugyouKenkyuu will help re-establish standard mathematics quality, as it is known that the Philippines ranked 78th among the 79 other countries worldwide in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). This direct evidence that the quality of our mathematics in the light of academics is dim. JugyouKenkyuu has a promising potential to be of great help, as evidenced by the data gathered. Japan's consistent and very good achievement in international education tests is attributed to the Japanese Lesson Study (L.S.), a school-based collaborative professional development activity [22] (Ebaeguín& Stephens, 2014).

Differentiated Instruction Modules

As a relevant output based on the results and findings of the study, differentiated modules on the following topics: functions; rational functions; exponential, inverse, and logarithmic functions were developed.

Conclusion

JugyouKenkyuu (Lesson Study) is a better teaching approach in helping students develop cognitive skills to understand General Mathematics and improve their mathematics performance. It has a significant effect on developing teachers' competencies, enhancing teaching quality, and promoting school change.

Recommendations

Future studies on other levels of education like tertiary education applying JugyouKenkyuu and in the other disciplines of Mathematics and other nationalities are recommended.

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